

THE ROLE OF *DIVASWAP* IN *ROGOTPATTI*: A COMPILATION FROM *BRIHATTRAYI*

Monika Goswami^{1*}, Dr. Meena Tandle², Dr. Vedbhushan Maitani³

¹*PG Scholar in Dept. of Ayurved Samhita Evam Siddhant.

^{2,3}Associate Professor Dept. of Ayurved Samhita Evam Siddhant.

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*Corresponding Author

Monika Goswami

PG Scholar in Dept. of Ayurved
Samhita Evam Siddhant.

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ABSTRACT

According to *Rogotpatti*, Ayurveda views lifestyle (Ahara and Vihara) as crucial to both disease manifestation and health maintenance. *Divaswap* (daytime sleep) is one of many lifestyle practices that have been extensively discussed in classical Ayurvedic texts, with both positive and negative effects. As explained in *Brihatrayi*, *The Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, this review article investigates the role of *Divaswap* in the pathogenesis of diseases (*Rogotpatti*). The indications, contraindications, pathogenesis, and specific diseases that result from daytime sleep have all been attempted to be compiled. have also made an effort to combine traditional wisdom with a modern perspective on health and illness.

KEYWORDS: Divaswap, Day time sleep, Diwaswapn, Diwaswap, Diwasvap.

INTRODUCTION

For the maintenance of health, Ayurveda consistently stresses the significance of daily routine (*Dinacharya*) and appropriate *Ratricharya* (*Nidra*). Daytime sleep, or *Divaswap*, has been suggested in some circumstances, even though nighttime sleep is thought to be crucial for both mental and physical renewal. *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya* are the classical texts that offer deep insights into the effects of daytime sleep and its contribution to the development of disease (*Rogotpatti*). In the modern era, when sedentary lifestyles and irregular sleep patterns are prevalent, it is critical to comprehend these ideas.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to

- Compile the knowledge shared on *Divaswap* in *Brihatrayi*
- To compile indications and contraindications stated in various Samhitas.
- Diseases caused due to *Divaswap*
- Correlation and contribution in disease occurrence in today's time.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

- Charak Samhita, Sushrut Samhita & Ashtang Hridaya
- Journals
- Internet
- Literary review

Review of literature: *Divaswap* in Ayurvedic Samhitas

1. Charaka Samhita

देहवृत्तो यथाहारस्तथा स्वप्नः सुखो मतः।

स्वपनहार समुत्थे च स्थौल्यकारश्ये विशेषतः॥

च. सु. २१/५१^[1]

As a person required right food for maintenance of health, likewise he needs regulated and timely sleep since obesity or leanness of the body is an outcome of food and sleep practiced by him.

Contraindication of excessive sleep

मेदस्विनः स्नेहनित्याः श्लेष्मलाः श्लेष्मरोगिनः।

दूशिविशः ारतश्चः दिवा न शयीरन कदाचन॥

च. सु. २१/५५^[2]

Divaswap is generally contraindicated for healthy people, people suffering from kapha prakriti evam vikriti, those affected by dushivish.

It is mentioned that sleeping during the day can cause Pitta and Kapha to get vitiated, particularly in people who eat lot of heavy, greasy foods and lead sedentary lifestyles.

Indication of day time sleep

Acharya Charaka has listed particular circumstances in which sleeping during the day is acceptable:

- For people with Kshaya, atisar (diarrohea), or after prolonged physical activity that leaves them exhausted
- For children, the elderly, the weak, and the injured
- During periods of extreme fatigue
- Those suffering from tamak shwas, hikka,
- During summer (Grishma Ritu).

Diseases caused by Divaswap

भवेन्नृणाम दिवास्वपनस्य अहितस्य निषेवणात्।

तस्मात् हितहितम स्वप्नं बुद्ध्वा स्वप्यात् सुखम बुधः॥

च. सु. २१/४९^[3]

Halimak (a type of jaundice), *Shirahshul* (headache), *Staimitya* (timidness), *Gurugatrata* (heaviness of the body), *Angamard* (malaise), *Agninash* (diminution of digestive power), *Hridaya Pralep* (a feeling as if phlegm adhered to the heart), *Shotha* (edema), *Arochak* (anorexia), *hrillas* (nausea), *Pinas* (rhinitis), *Ardhava bhedak* (hemicrania), *Kotha* (urticaria), *Aru* (eruption), *Pidaka* (abcess), *Kandu* (pruritus), *Tandra* (drowsiness), *Kas* (coughing), *Galamay* (diseases of the throat), *Smriti-Buddhi Pramoha* (impairment of the memory and intelligence), *Srotasaam avrodha* (obstruction of the circulating channels of the body), *Jwara* (fever), *Indriyanam asamarthata* (weakness of sensory and motor organs).

Further, the pathophysiology of

- *Prameha* (metabolic disorders like diabetes),
- *Sthaulya* (obesity) and
- *Agnimandya* (digestive fire impairment)

is said to be directly caused by excessive or inappropriate daytime sleep. *Tandra* (sleepiness), *Manda smriti* (memory impairment), *Agni* suppression and *Kapha* agitation are the main outcomes of day time sleep which eventually cause these diseases.

2. Sushruta Samhita

The effects of Divaswap are also acknowledged by Sushruta Samhita (Sharir Sthan 4/37), which also explains its function in Rogotpatti.

.. विकृतिर्हि दिवास्वपनो नाम, तत्र सवप्तामधर्माः सर्वदोषप्रकोपश्च, तत प्रकोपाच्च कास - श्वास-प्रतिश्याय - शिरोगौरव अंगमर्द अरोचक - ज्वर - अग्निदोर्बल्यानि भवन्ति.

सु शा ४/ ३७^[4]

Charaka's theory that daytime sleep raises Kapha and results in mandata (sluggishness) is supported by Sushruta.

Further, the Sushruta Samhita states that

- Daytime sleep causes Srotas (distribution channels) to become obstructed
- It plays a role in the Samprapti (pathogenesis) of Kapha-pradhana disorders.
- Sleeping during the day can exacerbate psychological conditions like Apasmara (epilepsy) and Unmada (insanity).

3. Ashtanga Hridaya

In Ashtanga Hridaya (Sutrasthana chapter 7/ 55-61)^[5], Acharya Vagbhata combines the teachings of Sushruta and Charaka to offer a more condensed and useful perspective.

- Ratri jagran is raukshyakar (dryness causing) and day time sleep (Divaswap) is snigdhar.
- Divaswap is one of the main Nidanas (causative factors) for Kapha disorders, he explains.
- It results in the formation of Ama (undigested metabolic produce), which is the cause of numerous symptoms of disease.
- It directly results in body heaviness, fatigue, and disturbed Balance between Vata and Kapha

Acharya Vagbhata cautions against frequent indulgence but permits Divaswap under specific circumstances, such as those outlined in the Charaka Samhita.

Samprapti: Rogotpatti pathophysiology

The central mechanism causing diseases is

- **Kapha Vriddhi, or Kapha Growth** Sleeping during the day enhances the qualities of cold (Sheet), heavy (guru), and static (mand), which aggravates Kapha.
- **Weak digestive fire, or Agni Mandya:** Agni suppression results in metabolic disruption and the production of Ama.
- **Channel blockage, or Srotorodha:** Increased Ama and Kapha obstruct bodily channels, resulting in illness and stagnation (Srotorodh).
- **Dosha imbalance, or Dosha Vaishamy:** Mental and physical sluggishness result from an increase in Kapha and a suppression of Vata.

Summary of Diseases Attributed to Improper *Divaswap*.

Disease	Samhita References	Description
<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Charaka, Vagbhata</i>	Metabolic syndrome/Diabetes mellitus
<i>Sthaulya</i>	<i>Charaka, Vagbhata</i>	Obesity due to increased Kapha and Ama
<i>Agnimandya</i>	All	Loss of digestive power
<i>Tandra & Alasya</i>	All	Drowsiness and fatigue
<i>Apasmara & Unmada</i>	<i>Sushruta</i>	Worsening of mental health
<i>Kaphaja Jwara</i>	All	Fever due to Kapha predominance

DISCUSSION

It has been seen that all three samhitas have advocated against divaswap except under listed conditions. Also it is agreed by modern medicine, getting too much sleep during the day is linked to the following conditions:

- obesity,
- type 2 diabetes,
- cardiovascular disease,
- cognitive decline,
- depression and lethargy.

These ailments, as seen in today's time, signify their Samhita's relevance because they closely resemble the Ayurvedic illnesses illustrated in text to have been caused by Divaswap.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion According to all three *Brihatrayi* (Ayurvedic Samhitas), daytime sleep is generally contraindicated in healthy individuals, despite being advantageous in certain listed conditions.

Together, the classical illustrations of Charaka, Sushruta, and Vagbhata caution against its frequent use since it vitiates Kapha, hampers Agni, and sparks the development of disease processes. Therefore, even in todays context, where sedentary lifestyles and irregular sleep patterns are prevalent, this ancient wisdom is significant and relevant. Preventive healthcare and lifestyle management may benefit from the incorporation of these Ayurvedic principles.

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